

Madona Nikolaishvili

*Lecturer at the Faculty of Education and Social Sciences,
Tbilisi Free Academy
Tbilisi, Georgia;*

*Coach of USAID Basic Education Program
Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University
Telavi, Georgia*

CLASSROOM ACTIVITIES USING THE UNIVERSAL TEACHING TOOL “MADONA”

Annotation. In the paper, several examples of classroom activities are discussed using the universal tool of educational development, the “madona”. The author considers that the tool is universal, because it can be used successfully by the student and the teacher, while the student can use it during the work on the assignment and during the presentation of the work, and the teacher- during the assignment and evaluation of the work.

The instrument is a multifunctional table that is very easy to use. When starting work, the student uses the tool as a plan to complete tasks. It works on the task offered and simultaneously fills in each column. At the end of the work, the table already represents the student's reflections on the work done.

The teacher uses the mentioned instrument as a form of observation of the students during classroom work, and can also use it as an evaluation rubric and individual evaluation form to evaluate the achievements of each student and the entire class without wasting time and energy.

The tool develops critical thinking skills and values in accordance with the educational goals provided by the national curriculum: problem-solving skills, critical thinking, creative thinking, communication skills. One of the advantages of the instrument is also the promotion of the development of metacognitive skills.

Keywords: developing teaching, constructivism, instrument “madona”, transparent skills, metacognition.

Education is one of the most priority areas for our country's development, because the country's progress is impossible without an educated and progressive-minded new generation. In Georgia, the priority of education has been announced in the most effective document in the field of general education, “general education national goals”, which ensures the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of education and science. According to the mentioned document, the general education system in Georgia aims to create favorable conditions for the carrier of **national and general human values**, for the formation of a free personality, and one of the main means of achieving these goals is the national curriculum, which is based on a constructivist educational concept focused on personality development.

Constructivism (lat. Construction – arrangement, mutual arrangement of parts, complex structure, as well as its constituent individual parts) rejects the transmission of knowledge in a finished form to the student, because in this case the student remains only a passive recipient of the transmitted knowledge and it resembles a child who has memorized a foreign language

sentence, although he doesn't understand a single word and therefore, he won't use this knowledge in anything. The constructive approach implies the construction of knowledge by the student independently, step by step, based on previous knowledge. The teacher is also the organizer and facilitator of this process, he is the student's thinking stimulator and guide, and if necessary, help is provided only to the extent that, after receiving this help, the student can continue the knowledge acquisition process independently.

One of the founders of constructivism, *lev vygotsky* believes that learning should precede the child's cognitive development. This provision is one of the important principles of *vygotsky's* theory. In other words, this is learning for development. And anyway, what is the development of teaching? Developmental teaching is a type of learning activity that involves the active use of developmental tasks in the learning process. in the pedagogic term definition dictionary (author by J. Djindjikhadze), the principles of developmental learning are given: “development is taking place through the growth of the child's culture and is based on the achievements of his natural maturity; teaching is the source of development (it runs in the nearest development zone); the student must be the subject of learning and not an object (principle of subjectivity of the student in the learning process); teaching precedes development and leads to it (principle of teaching precedes); the principle of problem as a motivational condition; modeling principle; separation of four components in the structure of the training activity: training task, training action, control action and evaluation action; dialog-polylogist principle; deduction of information delivery”.

As education specialist M. Firchkhadze in his article, – “using developmental tasks in the lesson”, – writes: “diagnostic teaching somehow replaces group, explanation/comprehension oriented teaching and is more focused on the individualization of learning”. What are the advantages of individualized learning compared to group learning? The answer is simple: although group work has no positive features, such as mutual learning, the development of collaborative skills, the acceptance of different opinions, empathy, the activation of the sense of belonging, etc., during group work, often have the manifestations of the phenomenon of social laziness. As is well known, social boredom is the phenomenon of less productivity in group action compared to individual activity. This event is appropriate when, during any activity, the members of the group experience the anonymity of their participation in the overall event, when they believe that their contribution to the final outcome of the collective action is unknown. On the other hand, each member thinks that the other is putting less effort into the overall work, so he himself tries to reduce the effort, which is undoubtedly a hindering factor for the child's development.

The concept of developmental learning is based on the student's closest development zone, because as mentioned above, mainly the learning taking place in the closest development zone is the source of the child's development, while such tasks, which the child can perform independently, contribute less to his development. “**Nearest development zone**” is the central concept of I. Vygotsky's theory, one of the foundations of constructivism. According to this theory, the closest zone of development is the difference between the current level of the child's

development and the potential level. The current level of development is the maximum of the child's abilities, that is, the upper limit of the difficulty of the tasks that the child can solve without the help of others, independently, while the potential level of development means the upper limit of the difficulty of the tasks that the child can solve with the help of someone else, a more competent peer, or the teacher.

Based on the above, the modern teacher is faced with a number of challenges: he must correctly define the closest zone of the child's development and select the appropriate tasks for this zone, keep in mind that the task must be interesting and motivating for the student, fully meet the subject standards, be connected to the child's life experience, at the same time, the art of scaffolding must be thoroughly mastered in order to provide help to the student at the right time and dose, at the same time observe the student's task performance process, evaluate the developing feedback, if necessary use differentiated learning approaches, remediation, etc.

We probably all agree that the listed challenges are quite hard work for teachers and require a lot of time and energy. Therefore, education theorists should probably think more about the issue of how to make the implementation of their obligations practical. It is for this purpose that the developmental learning tool “madona” was created. By its very nature, “madona” is a universal tool, because it can be used successfully by both the student and the teacher, and the student can also use it during the work process and during the presentation of work, while the teacher can use it when giving assignments and evaluating work.

madona

m	macro concept → main data
a	association
d	dynamic
o	operate
n	novation
a	audience

Pupil:-----

The tool intended for pupil is a simple two-world and six-line table that is multifunctional and at the same time very easy to use. When starting work, the student uses the tool as a plan to complete tasks. It works on the task offered and simultaneously fills in each column. At the end of the work, the table already represents the student's reflections on the work done. First, it is necessary to define the purpose of each graph.

Macro concept and related main data:

Macro is a greek word, it is the first component of complex words and means big, large, and the concepts are defined according to the national curriculum as the basis of systematic and comprehensive knowledge of the subject. Therefore, the concepts are an integral part of the result and the target orientation of the learning process. The learning of concepts includes its three structural elements: the term (meaningful word), the content of concepts (the essential characteristics of concepts) and the volume of concepts (the number of examples/cases to which these characteristics apply). E.g. One of the components of the assessment of mathematical tasks is the knowledge and use of mathematical concepts and provisions. In this case, a large learning unit will be written in the graph – the general concept and the essential data related to it from the task conditions.

Association – is a latin word and means connection. In psychology, this is the kind of connection between representations, when one representation leads to another according to similarity, contrast or proximity. E.g. In our case, it will be the activation of previous knowledge related to the new task from the stock of knowledge that already exists in the student's mind.

Dynamic- is a greek word and in one definition it means the change of any event, the course of development. In relation to the instrument to be discussed, this will be the student's "kata poda" (step by step) – understanding and argumentation of the consistency of the procedures to be performed.

Operate – (Lat. Operae-jobs) - any work, physical, mental. In this case, it means the correct performance of each procedure listed in the previous graph.

Innovation – (Lat.novatio- update) the pupil mentions, what was the news for him, he "found" when completing these tasks.

Audience (Lat. Auditorium) – the term has the meaning of lectures, lectures and others. The unity of the listeners. In the reviewed instrument, this graph involves the presentation of the worker to the class, his answers to the questions asked, the pupil's emotions during the interaction with the audience, and generally the pupil's reflections on the work performed.

Consider several examples of tasks using the "madona" tool.

I assignment (VI class)

direction: geometry and space perception;

general concept (marcoconcept): geometric transformations (symmetry)

according to the subject standard of mathematics, the result to be achieved: the pupil must be able to demonstrate geometric transformations.

Task conditions: once upon a time, the neighboring prince of the kingdom invited to the council. Princes decided to wear a new dress to the party and went to the best tailor in the kingdom. But unfortunately, the tailor became ill prince was forced to buy a dress for a apprentice. The apprentice really wanted the dress to turn out beautiful, he decorated it with a collar, cuffs, pockets, buttons, embossed lines, but despite this, the dress still did not turn out beautiful. Princes was very worried, she didn't know what to do with the dress.

Look at the pictures. In your opinion, what are the flaws of the dress? Advise the princess how to correct these errors; in your opinion, how will you change the dress? How to correct errors?

Task created using case-based learning method. In addition to developing real problem-solving skills, this method develops creative thinking, analytical thinking, question formulation and argumentation skills, presentation skills, etc.

Before completing the table, the pupil will familiarize himself with the terms and drawings.

Macro – concepts it will be written in the graph geometric transformations (symmetry) and related essential data, eg. Artistic details such as the collar, pocket, cuffs, relief lines on the gusset on the right and left sides of the dress are not symmetrically arranged.

In the association graph, the pupil remembers the condition of symmetry. It should also be noted that it is not necessary, previous knowledge must be related only to mathematics. It is quite possible for the pupil to remember how he made a doll's dress in art class, how he folded the fabric twice before cutting it so that both sides came out the same with respect to the folding line. Or at least for the New Year's Eve, cut out the whistles from the folded paper.

It will be written in the dynamics graph, what procedures should be performed and why. E.g. 1. The corner is narrow and rounded on one side, and wide and angular on the other side. Because the narrow, rounded part cannot be enlarged, the wider part must be narrowed and rounded. 2. There are different numbers of relief lines on the gorge. Because making a new wreath is easier than removing the existing one, a third relief wreath must be added on the left side. 3. The left relief line coming out of the year must be extended and extended to the right. 4. The pockets are located at different heights. It is necessary to lift the right pocket up to the same height, because it is very close to the waistline and the pocket is not recognized. 5. The cuffs have different shapes and sizes. It is not possible to change any of them so that they are identical to each other.

It will be written in the operating graph, each error correction procedure must be recorded, eg. The pupil first draws the axis of symmetry, then corrects all the flaws on the same

drawing according to the rules of the symmetrical figure of the given figure and prepares the model of the dress to be presented to the class.

It will be written in the innovation graph, for example, the news for the pupil was that he saw firsthand how useful and useful geometric transformations are, namely the knowledge of symmetry to solve a specific existing problem.

In the audience graph, the pupil describes the process of presenting his work, what questions were asked by the teacher and classmates, how he solved these questions, what he was satisfied with, what he did not like, what he changed, if he had to do such a task again, etc.

The tool “madona” can be successfully used with students of different age groups, as well as when teaching different subjects. Below we offer an example of the use of the mentioned tool in the georgian language and literature lesson in the first grade.

II task (I class)

Topic: speech; etiquette forms of speech

Macro concept: speaking, reading, writing.

According to the georgian subject standard, the result to be achieved: the pupil should be able to use familiar vocabulary and language-syntax constructions appropriately; protection of the basic norms of correct speech and speech etiquette; acting out the read text by name, filling in the missing information in the simple text of a familiar topic; compose simple short pragmatic texts using model, cues/supports.

Task conditions: insert the following words in the missing places **1. Please, 2. If possible, 3. Thanks, 4. Excuse me, 5. Do you wanna?**

In the store

- _____ **how much this toy?**

14 lari. – _____ **will you show?**

- _____ **please show me**

This toy – _____

I buy this toy, take the money

- _____ **a change**

- _____

After filling in the text, play the roles of seller and buyer in pairs.

m	speaking, reading, writing-completing the missing text and role-playing with various speech roles offered;
a	which words do we use more often when buying?
d	the appropriate place must be found for the given words
o	1. excuse me 2. do you wanna? 3. if possible 4. please 5. thank you
n	playing the roles of seller and buyer is very enjoyable
a	the children liked my played role, they gave me a question, when I go into a real store, I use these questions? it was difficult to answer.

Madona

The “madona” tool can be used during the integrated lesson. In such a case, it is possible to add tables for each subject separately or add columns for the second subject. The task of the mathematical part of the integrated lesson of mathematics and Georgian is discussed below:

III assignment (IX class)

Topic: mathematical models of real processes;

General concept (macro concept): algebraic images; equations and equations (quadratic triangles, square triangles)

According to the mathematics subject standard, the result to be achieved: the pupil should be able to write verbally the described situation as an algebraic image (formula); solution of equations; compilation of equations verbally according to given tasks.

Task conditions: if we add the sum of the squares of two consecutive natural numbers, we will get a number that refers to N. Baratashvili's famous poem “the fate of kartli”. Date of writing compile the equation, find these numbers and write them down so that you get an important date from the poet's biography.

--	--	--	--

Madona

m	algebraic images; equations. general date are: 2 consecutive natural numbers, sorting in the square, total, completion, date of writing of the poem						
a	finding the roots of quadratic angles, entering the variables needed to compile the equations. the poem “the fate of kartli” was written in 1839.						
d	first of all, you need to set up the image. if the first number is marked with x, its next number will be x+1, and the sum of their squares will be $x^2 + (x+1)^2$. as a result of the expansion, we will get $(x^2 + (x+1)^2)*3$. received image will be equal 1839. we get a square equation.						
o	$(x^2 + (x+1)^2)*3=1839$ $(2x^2 + 2x + 1)*3=1839$ $6x^2 + 6x - 1836 = 0$ $x^2 + x - 306 = 0$ $D=1-4*(-306)=1225=35^2$	$x_1 = \frac{-1-35}{2} = -18$. X= -18, X+1= -7 $x_2 = \frac{-1+35}{2} = 17$. X= 17, X+1= 18 -18 and -17 are negative numbers and it doesn't work, and on the 17th and 18th, if you write it in the given table, we'll get	<table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">8</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="width: 20px; text-align: center;">7</td> </tr> </table> n. baratashvili date of birth.	1	8	1	7
1	8	1	7				
n	I discovered two pairs of roots -18; -17 and 17; 18 coordinates are numbers arranged symmetrically to the heads.						
a	during the presentation of the work, my classmates asked me questions: 1.why wasn't one of the roots useful? -18 and 2. why the -18-c sign fell. answer: 1. according to the terms of the contract, both numbers were natural, therefore -18 does not apply. 2. -18's sign didn't fall off, the second number is accepted taking into account the order of the assignments (or next to each other)						

Madona

Option 1

criteria	1 level	2 level	3 level
macro concept – Main data			
association			
dynamics			
operate			
novatio			
audience			

Option 2

N 1	name, surname	m	a	d	o	n	a	note
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								

Option 3

m	a	d	o	n	a	

As for the teacher-specific tools, due to its multi-functionality, we can use several variations of it: I represent the evaluation rubric and it is similar to the one intended for the student, with the difference that, depending on the teacher's wishes, it has four or five columns. The first column lists the evaluation criteria, and the rest - performance indicators according to the levels of maturity. II – It is similar to the checklist and is used to observe the pupil's work. There are three-level graphs along each line, in which the teacher indicates which level corresponds to a particular pupil's work process or created product. The last column is intended for notes, where the teacher makes notes, based on which evidence he marked this or that level. These records will be used during the pupil's developmental assessment. III or short form is used for individual assessments. According to the levels, appropriate feedback is required.

As mentioned above, the presented tool is designed to help both pupil and teacher. But this alone does not exhaust its universality. It can be used by any subject teacher. The tool is flexible and allows you to use it when performing different types of tasks.

The tool develops the pupil's skills and values in accordance with the teaching-learning goals provided by the national curriculum: problem solving, because when completing tasks, he needs to search for ways to solve the problem, select the most effective of them, critical thinking, because it requires argumentative reasoning, that is, suitable arguments to substantiate his own opinions, example movers; you will create thinking, because it pushes him to accept challenges and take bold steps in school activities; communication, because it makes the student experience something, bring the idea to the audience/reader, and make an impression on them. One of the advantages of the instrument is also the promotion of the development of metacognitive skills, because it includes all the activities necessary for the development of these skills. These activities are: modeling strategies, prior metacognitive pause and subsequent metacognitive pause. Each graph of the tool helps the student understand how to perform this activity. In its essence, it is the modeling of strategies; the tool obliges the pupil to determine the way in which he will perform the task, to describe in detail the stages of the task, to think about how to present his work, what questions he will have to answer, to justify the appropriateness of the selected ways or strategies, in other words, this is a preliminary metacognitive pause. And during the subsequent metacognitive pause stage, the pupil remembers and describes the progressed path, realizes how well he performed the task, what he did next, what techniques he used while working, what was difficult or what was easy, what mistakes he found, what he would improve himself. The metacognitive pause does not develop the students' learning skills and increases their learning ability.

Based on the examples discussed, we can conclude that "Madona" is an innovative tool for developmental learning, the use of which allows the teacher to select adequate teaching strategies during the study of each specific topic, which makes the learning process diverse, interesting and productive, reduces disciplinary problems, because in such lessons it increases pupils activity, initiative, efficiency and degree of involvement in the learning process; introduce problem-oriented teaching in daily practice; the pedagogic process is conducted with such problematic situations, which does not involve the transfer of advanced knowledge to the pupil, but forces him to solve problems artificially provoked by the teacher (or given in the teaching material). In addition, considering the tool's multi-functionality, use it as a developmental assessment tool to assess the achievements of each pupil and the entire class without wasting time and energy. For the pupil, it represents the sequence of steps necessary to complete the tasks and gives the way, stimulates thinking. Verbalization of performed actions contributes to the development of reasoning skills. The pupil has to plan activities/procedures – understanding the requirements and determining the knowledge needed to perform them; determination of the main purpose of tasks/activities; outlining the stages of work; to predict what will be made easier,

what will be made difficult, in what matter will he need help? Targeted selection of strategies for each stage of work, accordingly, he develops many important skills.